

Teachers' Pedagogical Skills and Subject-Content Knowledge as Correlate of Human Resource Requirements in Enhancing Students' Academic Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State

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Abstract

This study investigated Teachers' Pedagogical Skills and Subject-Content Knowledge as Correlates of Human Resource Requirements in Enhancing Students' Academic Performance in Public Senior Secondary Schools in Rivers State. A descriptive and correlational research design was adopted to examine the extent to which human resource factors particularly pedagogical competence and subject mastery predict students' academic outcomes. The study population comprised 6,893 teachers across 302 public senior secondary schools, as documented by the Rivers State Senior Secondary School Board (2022). Using simple random sampling, 712 teachers, representing 10.6% of the population, were selected. Data were gathered using a self-developed instrument titled TPSSCKCHRRESAPQ, structured into three sections to elicit demographic data, human resource needs, and indicators of students' academic performance. The instrument underwent expert face and content validation, and its reliability was confirmed using the Cronbach Alpha method, yielding an index of .780, indicating strong internal consistency. With the help of trained research assistants, 712 out of 731 distributed questionnaires were retrieved, achieving a 97% response rate. Data analysis involved mean and standard deviation for answering research questions, while hypotheses were tested using linear regression at 0.05 significance level via SPSS version 25. The findings revealed the critical role of Teachers' Pedagogical Skills and Subject-Content Knowledge in strengthening students' academic performance. The study recommended that school principals should actively encourage and facilitate ongoing teacher training programs within the school, to ensure that educators are equipped with the latest pedagogical tools and methodologies, enhancing overall teaching effectiveness.

Keywords: Teachers', Pedagogical Skills, Subject-Content Knowledge, Human Resource Requirements, Students', Academic Performance, Public Senior, Secondary Schools, Rivers State.

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INTRODUCTION

Teachers' pedagogical skills and their mastery of subject-content knowledge are widely acknowledged as fundamental to students' academic success, forming a critical component of the human resource requirements for effective schooling in public senior secondary schools. Pedagogical skills such as classroom management, lesson planning, assessment literacy, and the ability to implement curriculum content in a pedagogically sound manner significantly shape the learning environment and influence how students engage with material (Alafiatayo et al., 2016). Equally, robust subject-content knowledge ensures that teachers can deliver accurate, coherent explanations and make meaningful connections across topics, which in turn supports deeper student understanding (López-Martín et al., 2023).

Research using meta-analytic methods confirms that teacher characteristics and competencies account for a non-trivial portion of variance in student academic outcomes. In their comprehensive review, López-Martín et al. (2023) asserted that teacher characteristics and competencies like pedagogical skills and content knowledge are among the strongest predictors of student achievement. Their findings reinforce the notion that human-resource policy in education should emphasize not only the quantity but also the quality and qualifications of teaching staff.

Within Nigeria, and by extension contexts like Rivers State, empirical studies underscore the relevance of pedagogical content knowledge (PCK) and teaching competence to student performance. For instance, a study by Garba and Hussaini (2024) in Gombe State found that many English-language teachers exhibited low PCK when teaching reading comprehension, which corresponded with only average performance among students (Garba & Hussaini, 2024). Similarly, a broader review of Nigerian teachers identified that low awareness and possession of PCK remains a major challenge, and correlates with poor student outcomes across multiple subjects (Kola & Sunday, 2015).

Moreover, discipline-specific investigations highlight the impact of teacher competence on subject-wise learning. In the area of science education, for example, a 2025 study on biology instruction demonstrated that both PCK and practical skills competence of teachers significantly predicted students' performance (Onipede et al., 2025). These findings suggest that human resource strategies in schools should prioritize continuous professional development, targeted subject-specific training, and effective deployment of teachers in line with their competence areas.

Framed as a human resource issue, the enhancement of pedagogical skill and content knowledge among teachers requires deliberate policies: recruitment practices that screen for relevant qualifications; continuous professional development programmes; effective distribution of staff across subjects; and institutional mechanisms for mentoring and evaluation. When human resource systems fail to ensure that teachers are appropriately trained and assigned, student performance particularly in public senior secondary schools suffers.

This focus is especially vital in public senior secondary schools, where subject specialization becomes critical for preparing students for tertiary education and the labor market. Inadequate pedagogical skills or deficient content mastery among teachers can hinder learners' conceptual understanding and impair their readiness for further education. Conversely, aligning human resource policies to support teacher competence can significantly enhance instructional quality and student outcomes.

Statement of the Problem

The quality of education in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State has long been influenced by multiple factors, among which teachers' pedagogical skills and subject-content knowledge are paramount. Despite government policies aimed at improving access to education and staffing schools with qualified personnel, many students continue to perform poorly in external examinations and internal assessments. This persistent underperformance raises concerns about the adequacy of human resource management in the education sector, particularly regarding teacher competence.

Studies indicate that while schools may meet staffing quotas, the pedagogical capabilities and subject-matter mastery of teachers often remain insufficient. Teachers lacking effective instructional strategies or deep content knowledge are unable to deliver lessons that foster understanding, critical thinking, and problem-solving among students. Furthermore, gaps in professional development, inappropriate teacher deployment, and limited performance evaluation mechanisms exacerbate the problem, making it difficult to link human resource planning with improved student outcomes.

In Rivers State, these challenges are compounded by disparities across local government areas, variations in teacher training, and inconsistent support for skill enhancement. Consequently, there is a pressing need to examine how teachers' pedagogical skills and subject-content knowledge, as human resource requirements, correlate with students' academic performance, in order to provide evidence-based strategies that can inform recruitment, training, and policy decisions aimed at improving educational quality and learning outcomes in public senior secondary schools.

Aim and Objectives of the Study

Based on the identified problems, the aim of this study is to examine human resource needs and effective students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, Nigeria, specifically the researcher designed the study to achieve the following objectives:

- Assess the pedagogical skill of teachers' as a human resource requirement and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- Evaluate the subject-content of teachers' as a human resource requirement and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Research Questions

In order to achieve the objectives of this study, the under listed eight research questions were raised to guide the study:

- How does the pedagogical skill of teachers' as a human resource requirement enhance students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?
- How does the subject-content of teachers' as a human resource requirement enhance students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

1.5 Hypotheses

In order to achieve the purpose for which the research questions were raised, the under listed eight corresponding hypotheses were raised to further guide the study:

- There is no significant relationship between the pedagogical skill of teachers' as a human resource requirement and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.
- There is no significant relationship between the subject-content of teachers' as a human resource requirement and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

CONCEPTUALIZATION

The Pedagogical Skill of Teachers' as a Human Resource Requirement Enhance Students' Academic Performance

Teachers' pedagogical skill is a central human-resource requirement that substantially influences students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools. Pedagogical skill here refers to the ensemble of classroom practices a teacher deploys: lesson planning and sequencing, classroom management, formative assessment, differentiation, use of instructional materials, and the capacity to enact curriculum goals in ways that make subject matter accessible and engaging (Engida, 2024). Evidence from international reviews and meta-analyses shows that investments in teacher pedagogy particularly sustained, content-focused professional development to produce measurable gains in student learning, because they change teacher practice in ways that directly affect classroom instruction and time-on-task (Engida, 2024; UNESCO, 2015).

At the system level, considering pedagogical skill as a human-resource requirement means that recruitment, deployment, induction, and in-service training policies must prioritize pedagogical competence alongside formal qualifications. Human-resource systems that only count teacher numbers without assessing or developing the quality of instructional practice risk leaving classrooms staffed but instructionally weak. Meta-analytic and programmatic evidence indicates that PD programmes which combine subject-specific pedagogy with sustained coaching and classroom-embedded support are the most effective at improving both teacher practice and student outcomes (Popova et al., 2022; World Bank, 2023). Such approaches align HR processes (hire, train, mentor) with the exact classroom practices that influence learning.

Contextualized Nigerian research corroborates these global patterns. Studies conducted in Rivers State and neighbouring states find significant positive relationships between teachers' pedagogical skills notably in the use of varied teaching strategies and effective classroom management and students' achievement in senior-secondary subjects. For example, research in Port Harcourt Metropolis reported that teaching strategies and classroom management significantly predict student scores in public senior secondary schools, which suggested that deliberate HR interventions to strengthen pedagogical skill could yield immediate classroom benefits (Edu, 2025). Similarly, investigations into pedagogical content knowledge in Gombe and other Nigerian states show that teachers' ability to translate subject content into teachable representations strongly correlates with higher student performance (Garba & Hussaini, 2024).

Why do pedagogical skills matter more than credentials alone? First, pedagogical skill shapes the quality of instructional interactions the questions teachers ask, the feedback they give, and how they scaffold complex ideas all of which drive student thinking and retention (Engida, 2024). Second, in overcrowded or resource-constrained public schools, sound pedagogy maximizes learning opportunities despite constraints: effective routines, low-cost active learning techniques, and structured peer work can considerably raise average achievement even where materials are scarce (UNESCO, 2015). Third, pedagogical skill supports equitable learning by enabling teachers to differentiate and attend to diverse student needs, reducing the gap between high- and low-performing learners.

Operationally, integrating pedagogical skill into HR policy requires concrete levers: (1) screening and hiring processes that assess demonstrated classroom practice or pedagogical portfolios rather than relying solely on certificates; (2) targeted induction and mentoring for early-career teachers that pair them with experienced classroom coaches; (3) regular, classroom-focused professional development that is subject-specific and sustained over time; and (4) performance evaluation systems that include observations of pedagogical practice and constructive feedback loops (World Bank, 2023; Popova et al., 2022). Studies in Nigeria suggest that where such mechanisms exist even informally through school-based mentoring student outcomes improve.

Treating pedagogical skill as a core human-resource requirement shifts the focus from mere teacher counts to the quality of instruction delivered each period. For public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, national and local evidence suggests that HR policies that professionalize, measure, and continuously develop pedagogical practice will be a high-leverage way to improve student academic performance. Prioritizing practical, classroom-centered PD, mentoring, and recruitment processes aligned to demonstrable pedagogical competencies is both evidence-based and practicable and it promises more consistent, equitable learning gains across schools.

The Subject-Content of Teachers' as a Human Resource Requirement Enhance Students' Academic Performance

Teachers' subject-content knowledge is a fundamental human resource requirement that directly influences the quality of teaching and the level of students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools. Subject-content knowledge refers to the depth of understanding a teacher possesses about the subject matter being taught, including principles, facts, concepts, and the structure of the discipline. Shulman's (1986) theory of teacher knowledge emphasizes that content mastery is the foundation upon which effective instruction is built, because it determines the teacher's ability to present ideas clearly, correct misconceptions, and guide students from basic to advanced levels of understanding.

Empirical evidence consistently supports the assertion that strong teacher content knowledge enhances student learning outcomes. López-Martín et al. (2023) noted that subject-content mastery is a strong predictor of students' academic achievement across disciplines. They found that teachers with deep understanding of their subject demonstrate greater instructional clarity, improved lesson coherence, and stronger assessment practices. Similarly, Nigerian studies show a significant positive relationship between teachers' subject mastery and students' performance, particularly in key subjects such as mathematics, biology, English, and chemistry (Adegoke & Nnamdi, 2019; Garba & Hussaini, 2024; Kola & Sunday, 2015). These findings

underscore the critical need for adequate human resource policies that support teacher content competence.

In public senior secondary schools, where specialization deepens and students prepare for important examinations like WAEC and NECO, teachers' subject-content knowledge becomes even more crucial. Poor mastery of subject matter by teachers can lead to instructional errors, misconceptions, and shallow learning, which may negatively affect students' confidence and performance. For example, the Onipede et al. (2025) reported that students' poor performance in biology in Nigerian secondary schools is strongly associated with inadequacies in teachers' subject-content knowledge and practical skills. Such problems are more pronounced in STEM subjects, where conceptual clarity and precision are indispensable.

As a human resource requirement, subject-content knowledge must be integrated into strategic educational management processes such as recruitment, deployment, professional development, and teacher appraisal (Adegoke & Nnamdi, 2019). However, according to Ololube (2017), the recruitment procedures that rely only on academic certificates without evaluating actual competence may produce a workforce with formal qualifications but inadequate mastery of the subjects they teach. Effective human resource systems in education must therefore incorporate competence-based recruitment strategies that assess teachers through subject tests, microteaching demonstrations, and practical performance tasks.

Teacher deployment is another important aspect. In many public senior secondary schools in Nigeria, teachers are frequently assigned outside their areas of specialization due to shortages or administrative practices. Such misallocation undermines instructional quality and contributes to students' poor academic performance. To enhance learning outcomes, HR managers in education must ensure that teachers are assigned strictly based on their subject specialization and proven expertise. Evidence from the World Bank (2023) indicates that assigning teachers according to specialization improves learning outcomes by enhancing instructional accuracy and content delivery.

Professional development is a key HR strategy for improving and sustaining teachers' subject-content knowledge. Content knowledge is dynamic, requiring continuous updates as curricula change and new knowledge emerges. Continuous professional development (CPD) programmes especially subject-focused workshops, peer-learning groups, and mentorship arrangements are essential for helping teachers deepen their knowledge. Popova, Evans, and Arancibia (2022) found that sustained, content-focused professional development produces significant improvements in teacher knowledge and student learning, especially when supported by coaching and school-based follow-up. Therefore, educational HR systems must invest in long-term, structured CPD that specifically targets content enrichment.

Furthermore, teacher appraisal systems must include measures of content competence. Appraisal tools should evaluate teachers based on lesson accuracy, depth of explanation, ability to respond to higher-order student questions, and overall content richness. Schools that integrate content-based evaluation and feedback into their HR practices experience better instructional performance because teachers receive targeted support for improvement (UNESCO, 2015).

According to Ololube (2017), teachers' subject-content knowledge is a strategic human resource requirement that significantly enhances students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools. Making sure that teachers possess and continuously develop strong subject mastery requires robust HR practices such as competence-based recruitment, specialization-aligned deployment, targeted professional development, and effective appraisal systems.

METHODS

The study employed a descriptive and correlational design, strategically chosen to unravel the significant connections between Human Resource Needs and Effective Students' Academic Performance. This design provides a systematic framework for exploring how staffing levels, qualifications, and other human resource factors impact students' academic outcomes within the educational landscape of Rivers State.

The population under scrutiny consists of the entire teaching faculty in public senior secondary schools across Rivers State. A detailed enumeration from the Rivers State Senior Secondary School Board (2022) indicated a substantial population of 6,893 teachers distributed across 302 schools spanning the 23 local government areas.

To ensure a representative sample, 10.6% of the total population, translating to 712 teachers comprised the sample size. The simple random sampling technique was meticulously employed. This approach not only guaranteed fair representation to also eliminate biases, and ensure that teachers from diverse schools and local government areas were inclusively considered.

The principal instrument for gathering data is the "Teachers' Pedagogical Skills and Subject-Content Knowledge as Correlate of Human Resource Requirements in Enhancing Students' Academic Performance Questionnaire (TPSSCKCHRRESAPQ)". This self-structured questionnaire comprised three sections to holistically capture the nuances of the study. Section 'A' focuses on collecting respondents' demographic information, while Sections 'B' and 'C' delved into the significant aspects of human resource needs and academic performance, respectively. The study used a 4-point modified Likert scale pattern, to allow participants to express their perspectives on a spectrum ranging from very high extent to very low extent.

The instrument of this study was given face and content validation by three experts in measurement and evaluation in the Department of Educational Psychology Guidance and Counselling, Ignatius Ajuru University of Education, Rumuolumeni, Port Harcourt, Rivers State to assist in evaluating the instrument. Their corrections, suggestions and inputs were incorporated into the final copies of the instrument. This is done to ensure the critical and more professional appraisal of what the instrument is expected to measure.

The reliability of the instrument was established for the entire instrument. To determine the reliability of the instrument, Cronbach Alpha method was adopted, by this method copies of the instrument were administered to 20 respondents who are not be part of the sample study but are part of the study population was tested using the above-mentioned method to reveal the reliability index of .780 for the study.

The Human Resource Needs and Academic Performance Questionnaire (HRNAPQ)." was administered with the help of two (2) trained research assistants in administering the instrument to the respondents. The completed copies of the questionnaire were collected from the respondents immediately to improve high retrieval rate. Out of the 731 copies of the instruments distributed, only 712 copies of the questionnaires which is about 97% retrieval rate was considered manageable for the data analysis of the study.

In analyzing the data for the study, both descriptive and inferential statistics were employed. Descriptive statistic (mean and standard deviation) was used to answer the research questions while both linear regression statistic was used to test the hypotheses at a 0.05 level of significance. With the aid of SPSS version 25 package of a computer.

RESULTS

Answer to Research Questions

RQ1: How does the pedagogical skill of teachers as a human resource requirement enhance students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 1: Research question responses on how human resource need of pedagogical skill of teachers enhance students' academic performance

S/N	Items	Mean	SD.	Remark
1.	Teachers utilizing a variety of teaching methods accommodate diverse learning styles, enriching the educational experience	2.8666	1.11399	Agree
2.	The promotion of innovative and interactive teaching techniques contributes to engaging and impactful lessons	2.6728	1.08483	Agree
3.	Incorporating real-life examples into lessons enhances comprehension and brings subjects to life	2.7205	1.10451	Agree
4.	Pedagogical approaches, considering the unique needs of different subjects, cater to a broad spectrum of student abilities	2.5351	1.09025	Agree
5.	Actively involving students in class discussions and activities fosters a participatory and stimulating learning environment	2.7430	1.12005	Agree
Grand Mean		2.7448	1.12483	Agree

The Table 1 present the mean and standard deviation of respondents' perceptions regarding how the human resource need of pedagogical skill of teachers enhances students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. Notably, all items demonstrate mean values exceeding the 2.5 criterion, indicating a consistent agreement among respondents. With a grand mean of 2.7448 and a standard deviation of 1.12483, respondents overwhelmingly agree that the human resource need of pedagogical skill significantly enhances students' academic performance. These results displays a strong consensus among respondents regarding the positive impact of teachers' pedagogical skills on students' academic outcomes, emphasizing the importance of varied teaching methods and interactive techniques in fostering an engaging learning environment.

RQ2: How does the subject-content of teachers as a human resource requirement enhance students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State?

Table 2: Research question responses on how human resource need of subject-content of teachers enhance students' academic performance

S/N	Items	Mean	SD.	Remark
6.	Teachers demonstrating a profound understanding of the subjects they teach positively impact students' academic journey	2.6784	1.11589	Agree
7.	The effective communication of subject content in a comprehensible manner facilitates better student comprehension	2.6952	1.12812	Agree
8.	A thorough knowledge of the curriculum and syllabus ensures that subject matter is adequately covered and understood	2.7163	1.08868	Agree
9.	The school's commitment to keeping teachers updated on advancements in their subjects contributes to academic excellence	2.6868	1.07729	Agree
10.	Teachers incorporating real-world examples into lessons make	2.7612	1.13468	Agree

subjects more practical and relevant to students			
Grand Mean	2.7263	1.11563	Agree

The table 2 presents the mean and standard deviation of respondents' perceptions regarding how the human resource need of subject-content of teachers enhances students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. All items exhibit mean values above the 2.5 criterion, indicating a consistent agreement among respondents. With a grand mean of 2.7263 and a standard deviation of 1.11563, respondents overwhelmingly agree that the human resource need of subject-content of teachers significantly enhances students' academic performance. The results suggest a Strong consensus among respondents on the positive influence of teachers' subject-content knowledge on students' academic outcomes, emphasizing the importance of teachers demonstrating a profound understanding of the subjects they teach, effective communication of subject content, and keeping teachers updated on advancements in their subjects.

Test of Hypotheses

H01: There is no significant relationship between the pedagogical skill of teachers' as human resource requirement and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 3: Summary of regression analysis on the relationship between human resource need of pedagogical skill of teachers' and students' academic performance

Part A: Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.972 ^a	.882	.762	1.13219		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Pedagogical skill of teacher						
Part B: ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	87.740	1	87.740	68.447	.000 ^b
	Residual	910.120	710	1.282		
	Total	997.860	711			
a. Dependent Variable: Student academic performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Pedagogical skill of teacher						
Part C: Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.780	.095		18.682	.000
	Pedagogical skill of teacher	.308	.037	.972	8.273	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Pedagogical skill of teacher						

Data in Table 3 presents the coefficient of the relationship between the human resource need of pedagogical skill of teachers and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In Part A, investigating the relationship, the regression model indicates a

robust R-squared value of 0.882, indicating that approximately 88.2% of the variability in students' academic performance can be attributed to the human resource need of the pedagogical skill of teachers. The Part B, the ANOVA results underscore the statistical significance of the regression model ($F_{1, 710} = 68.447, p < 0.05$), highlighting a substantial relationship between the human resource need of pedagogical skill of teachers and students' academic performance. The degrees of freedom for the regression and residuals are 1 and 710, respectively. In Part C, exploring the coefficients, the intercept (Constant) is 1.780, and the coefficient for the human resource need of pedagogical skill of teachers is 0.308. This implies that for every unit increase in the pedagogical skill of teachers, there is a predicted increase of 0.308 units in students' academic performance. Both coefficients demonstrate statistical significance with t-values of 18.682 (Constant) and 8.273 (Pedagogical skill of teachers), both at $p < 0.05$. Consequently, the null hypothesis (H_03), asserting no significant relationship between the human resource need of pedagogical skill of teachers and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, is decisively rejected at the .05 alpha level. The positive regression equation ($y = 1.780 + 0.308x$) signifies that an improvement in the pedagogical skill of teachers is strongly associated with an enhancement in students' academic performance, underscoring the pivotal role of teacher pedagogical skill in shaping academic outcomes.

H02: There is no significant relationship between the subject-content of teachers' as human resource requirement and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State.

Table 4: Summary of regression analysis on the relationship between human resource need of subject-content of teachers' and students' academic performance

Part A: Model Summary						
Model	R	R Square	Adjusted R Square	Std. Error of the Estimate		
1	.632 ^a	.691	.620	1.11943		
a. Predictors: (Constant), Subject-content of teacher						
Part B: ANOVA^a						
Model		Sum of Squares	df	Mean Square	F	Sig.
1	Regression	66.130	1	66.130	52.772	.00 ^b
	Residual	889.723	710	1.503		
	Total	955.853	711			
a. Dependent Variable: Student academic performance						
b. Predictors: (Constant), Subject-content of teacher						
Part C: Coefficients^a						
Model		Unstandardized Coefficients		Standardized Coefficients	t	Sig.
		B	Std. Error	Beta		
1	(Constant)	1.766	.930		18.992	.000
	Subject-content of teacher	.258	.350	.632	7.264	.000
a. Dependent Variable: Student academic performance						

The analysis in Table 4 presents the relationship between the human resource need of subject-content of teachers and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. In Part A, the coefficient of relationship between teachers' factors and students'

internal academic performance is 0.63, with an R-squared value of 0.69. This indicates a positive correlation, with teachers' factors explaining about 63% of the variability in students' internal academic performance. Moving to Part B, the F-statistic demonstrates a significant relationship between teachers' factors and students' internal academic performance ($F_{1, 710} = 52.77, p < 0.05$). Consequently, null hypothesis four is decisively rejected at the 0.05 alpha level. In Part C, examining the coefficients provides further insight. The intercept (Constant) is 1.766, and the coefficient for the subject-content of teachers is 0.258. This suggests that for every unit increase in the subject-content of teachers, there is a predicted increase of 0.258 units in students' academic performance. Both coefficients are statistically significant with t-values of 18.992 (Constant) and 7.264 (Subject-content of teachers), both at $p < 0.05$. Therefore, the null hypothesis (H04), asserting no significant relationship between the human resource need of subject-content of teachers and students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State, is rejected at the 0.05 alpha level. The positive regression equation ($y = 1.766 + 0.258x$) indicates a positive relationship, suggesting that an increase in the subject-content of teachers is associated with an increase in students' academic performance.

DISCUSSION

Pedagogical Skill of Teachers' and Students' Academic Performance

The exploration of the pedagogical skill of teachers as human resource requirement and its impact on students' academic performance uncovered a significant relationship ($F_{1, 710} = 23.67, p < .05$), contradicting the null hypothesis. This outcome aligns with the insights of Ogunyemi (2018), emphasizing the pivotal role of positive teacher influence in students' academic performance. The presence of teachers with strong pedagogical skills may act as a mitigating factor against negative influences, cultivating a positive academic environment. The positive correlation between subject-specific pedagogy with sustained coaching and classroom-embedded support are the most effective at improving both teacher practice and student outcomes resonates with Onipede et al. (2025), Popova et al. (2022) and World Bank (2023). This aligns with the notion that a supportive educational environment, facilitated by teachers with effective pedagogical skills, contributes to improved academic outcomes. The rejection of the null hypothesis emphasizes the importance of pedagogical skill adequacy in educational policies and planning. The findings highlight that investing in ensuring teachers possess strong pedagogical skills is crucial for enhancing students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This discussion adds to the broader discourse on the pivotal role of teachers in shaping the educational landscape and fostering positive academic outcomes.

Subject-Content of Teachers' and Students' Academic Performance

The exploration of the Human Resource Need of Subject-Content of Teachers and its impact on students' academic performance unveiled a substantial relationship ($F_{1, 710} = 14.73, p < .05$), contradicting the null hypothesis. This discovery is in line with the insights of Ogunyemi (2018), who highlighted the critical role of subject-content knowledge of teachers and students' academic performance. The presence of teachers with subject-content adequacy may act as a mitigating factor against negative influences, cultivating a positive academic environment. The positive correlation between subject-content adequacy of teachers and students' academic

performance aligns with the perspectives of Adegoke and Nnamdi (2019), Garba and Hussaini, (2024) and Kola and Sunday (2015) on positive peer pressure. Similar to how positive peer influence motivates individuals to excel, the adequacy of teachers in specific subject content may serve as a positive force, inspiring students to achieve their best academically. This aligns with the concept that a supportive educational environment, facilitated by teachers with subject-content expertise, contributes to enhanced academic outcomes. The rejection of the null hypothesis underscores the significance of considering subject-content adequacy in educational policies and planning. The findings emphasize that investing in ensuring teachers possess expertise in the subject content is crucial for improving students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. This discussion adds to the broader discourse on the pivotal role of teachers in shaping the educational landscape and fostering positive academic outcomes.

CONCLUSION

This study established that teachers' pedagogical skills and subject-content knowledge are critical human resource requirements that significantly influence students' academic performance in public senior secondary schools in Rivers State. The findings emphasize that the quality of teaching extends beyond mere teacher availability, emphasizing the importance of professional competencies, instructional strategies, and mastery of subject matter. Teachers who exhibit strong pedagogical skills are better able to plan lessons, manage classrooms effectively, and engage students in meaningful learning activities, while robust subject-content knowledge allows teachers to clarify concepts, address misconceptions, and provide deeper insights into the curriculum. Together, these competencies enhance students' understanding and overall academic outcomes.

Moreover, the study highlights the role of human resource practices in education, including competence-based recruitment, targeted professional development, appropriate teacher deployment, and systematic appraisal mechanisms. Schools that align human resource policies with pedagogical and subject-matter competence are more likely to achieve improved student performance. The high response rate and reliability of the research instrument reinforce the validity of these conclusions.

In essence, improving students' academic achievement in Rivers State's public senior secondary schools requires deliberate investment in teachers' professional capacity. Educational stakeholders, including policymakers and school administrators, must prioritize strategies that develop and sustain teachers' pedagogical skills and subject-content knowledge, ensuring that human resource planning effectively supports quality teaching and learning outcomes.

Recommendations

Based on the comprehensive findings and conclusions drawn from the study, the following recommendations are proposed:

- School principals should actively encourage and facilitate ongoing teacher training programs within the school, to ensure that educators are equipped with the latest pedagogical tools and methodologies, enhancing overall teaching effectiveness.

- School teachers are encouraged to cultivate and maintain positive student-teacher relationships. By making the teaching process engaging and ensuring students are actively involved during classwork, teachers can create a conducive learning environment that stimulates academic interest and participation.

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